

Fabrication of Smart Two Wheeler

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Abstract

In response to pressing environmental concerns and the depletion of fossil fuel resources, the automotive industry is actively exploring sustainable solutions. Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) have emerged as promising alternatives, integrating the strengths of conventional vehicles with the environmental benefits of electric power. Additionally, projects are addressing the need for innovation and smart features in vehicle design. Initiatives include the integration of GPS for locating the vehicle, a "Find My Vehicle" feature using sound technology, sophisticated display interfaces, and the overall transformation of vehicles into smart entities. These advancements collectively contribute to the ongoing evolution of hybrid vehicle technologies, aiming to address current challenges, enhance fuel economy, minimize environmental impact, and integrate smart functionalities for a more sustainable and technologically advanced future in transportation.

Keywords: Battery, Hybrid Two-wheeler, GPS Tracking, Internet of Things, Sensors.

I. Introduction

The automotive industry is undergoing a profound shift, compelled by the urgent need to confront environmental challenges, preserve finite fossil fuel reserves, and accommodate the rising demand for sustainable transportation options. In response to these imperatives, Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) have emerged as a transformative force poised to redefine vehicular mobility. While internal combustion engines have historically dominated, driven by the abundance of oil resources, heightened environmental awareness now questions this reliance due to the detrimental impact of emissions on air quality and public health. This scrutiny has catalysed the exploration of alternative propulsion technologies, leading to the rise of HEVs as a strategic compromise between conventional and electric power.

Across regions like Asia, where two-wheelers serve as lifelines for daily transportation needs, the pressing issues of escalating fuel consumption and emissions underscore the urgent need for sustainable solutions. In this context, hybrid technology emerges as a promising avenue, particularly well-suited for addressing the challenges of urban mobility. The development landscape for hybrid electric two-wheelers is marked by intensive research efforts focused on design optimization, component comparisons, and experimentation with energy management systems. The overarching goal of these endeavours is to engineer cost-effective solutions that facilitate a seamless transition towards more sustainable modes of transportation, aligning with the evolving needs of both users and the environment.

1.1. Advancements in Hybrid Technology:

- Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs): Offer extended electric range before switching to combustion mode.
- Battery Technology Improvements: Enhanced lithium-ion batteries improve energy density and performance.

- Regenerative Braking Enhancements: Capture more kinetic energy during braking for battery recharge.
- Lightweight Materials: Carbon fibre and alloys reduce weight, enhancing fuel efficiency.
- Smart and Predictive Technologies: Algorithms optimize power usage based on driving conditions.
- Wireless Charging: Research aims for convenient charging without cables.
- Increased Model Availability: More manufacturers offer hybrid options.
- Government Incentives: Subsidies promote hybrid and electric vehicle adoption.

II. Literature

Ruthvik P. Sankar et al. [1] discusses challenges related to petroleum-based vehicles, emphasizing resource depletion, inefficiencies, and environmental impact. It proposes Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) as a solution but notes high costs and long charging times for electric vehicles. The focus is on implementing hybrid technology in popular Asian two-wheelers. HEVs combine an internal combustion engine (ICE) and an electric motor for fuel efficiency and reduced emissions. Testing shows a 40.8% efficiency increase, successful Energy Management, and reduced CO₂ emissions. In conclusion, the hybrid two-wheeler offers a promising, sustainable, and environmentally friendly transportation option for urban commuting.

Atharva Teggi et al. [2] has proposed a smart bike system which integrates IoT technology to enhance security, automation, and safety features. It addresses increasing bike accident fatalities through GPS tracking, remote control, and sensors for speed control and collision avoidance. The system includes an emergency help feature and contributes to reducing bike accident fatalities; additionally it mentions a vehicle parameter monitoring and security system using IoT for monitoring fuel, tire pressure, and engine oil level, along with digital locks and GPS tracking. In conclusion, the smart bike system offers a comprehensive solution for enhancing bike security, safety, and maintenance in both urban and rural areas.

Shweta K. Narkhede et al. [3] highlights the shortcomings of existing security systems and emphasizes the need for a more reliable solution. One of the standout features of this device is its ability to provide efficient security for two-wheelers while also offering a convenient way to locate them, especially in crowded parking areas. This capability is made possible with a tilt sensor, which detects any movement or change in position of the vehicle from its stationary or leaning state.

Pooja V. Lokhande et al. [4] proposes that Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) are pivotal in the evolution towards sustainable transportation, merging the benefits of internal combustion engines and electric motors. They offer a practical solution by reducing emissions and fuel consumption without the range anxiety associated with electric vehicles (EVs).

Inzamam Ul Haq Rizvi et al. [5] highlights the growing importance of hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) as a response to increased vehicle usage and fossil fuel consumption contributing to air pollution. It introduces an innovative hybrid two-wheeler design that combines fuel and electric power, utilizing a motor directly linked to the gearbox for optimized performance. The study compares different hybrid configurations and advocates for a parallel hybrid approach to achieve better initial torque and high-speed efficiency. This approach integrates electric power in a unique way to enhance the vehicle's efficiency and reduce emissions.

Y. Kailash Nath Reddy et al. [6] the electric bike project outlined offers a sustainable and innovative solution to address environmental and economic concerns in transportation. By integrating a 1000-watt BLDC motor, a durable frame, and a high-capacity Lithium-ion battery with regenerative braking, it aims to enhance energy efficiency and extend battery range.

Harish N. et al. [7] shed light on the imperative need for environmentally sustainable transportation solutions, particularly pertinent in urban landscapes like India. They delineate the shortcomings of conventional internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, citing poor fuel economy and emissions as significant contributors to air pollution. Proposing a hybrid approach, integrating ICE technology with electric motor drive, the authors aim to enhance efficiency and curb emissions. Their review elucidates the working principles of a hybrid two-wheeler, detailing its operation in petrol, electric, and hybrid modes to optimize energy usage and mitigate pollution.

Rushi S. et al. [8] explore the development of hybrid electric two-wheelers, aiming to reduce on-road emissions and address consumer concerns about cost and complexity. Their research focuses on enhancing energy efficiency in small vehicles like scooters and motorcycles, achieved through a model integrating a 127cc GenSat Engine with a 24V, 120A heavy-duty DC electric motor. Control mechanisms involve a DC servo motor interfaced with an Arduino Mega 2560, enabling instruction via a human-machine interface projected on a laptop.

Mohd Hakimi Bin Zohari et al. [9] delve into the development of a GPS-based vehicle tracking system. Their study focuses on leveraging GPS technology to enhance vehicle tracking and monitoring capabilities. By utilizing GPS signals, the system enables real-time tracking of vehicle locations, providing valuable insights into fleet management, logistics, and security. The authors emphasize the significance of such systems in improving operational efficiency, optimizing route planning, and ensuring the safety and security of vehicles and cargo.

III. Objectives

The objectives of the project work are as follows:

- Develop a hybrid electric two-wheeler to minimize ecological impact and reduce carbon emissions compared to conventional vehicles.
- Incorporate GPS tracking, Find My Vehicle features.

IV. Methodology

Developing a smart hybrid 2-wheeler involves a comprehensive methodology that encompasses various stages from conceptualization to fabrication. Here is a step-by-step methodology for the fabrication of a smart hybrid 2-wheeler as shown in Figure 1 below.

V. Experimental Work

5.1 GPS Location Tracker with GSM Module

The GPS Location Tracker project aims to create a portable device that can track and share real-time location coordinates via SMS using an Arduino, a GPS module, and a GSM module. When a button is pressed, the system retrieves the GPS coordinates and sends them to a specified mobile number.

The GPS receiver module captures data in NMEA format. Arduino processes this data using the TinyGPS library to extract latitude and longitude coordinates. When the button is pressed, the GSM module sends an SMS containing the coordinates to a specified mobile number.

5.2 Find my vehicle

The mechanism can be activated remotely, through a dedicated remote control. This means that the vehicle owner can trigger the system from a distance, adding an extra layer of convenience and security.

5.3 Design Overview

The hybrid two-wheeler is designed to operate using two distinct power sources: an internal combustion engine (usually a small, efficient petrol engine) and an electric motor. The electric motor is integrated into the rear wheel hub, which is a compact and efficient placement that avoids the need for additional drivetrain components to transmit power from the motor to the wheel. The design overview of the two wheeler is as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Methodology of Project work

5.4 Control System

The vehicle likely incorporates a control system that manages the power output from both sources. It ensures smooth transition between modes, optimal performance, and safety. This system also prevents both power systems from being engaged simultaneously, which would lead to mechanical conflicts and inefficiencies.

Figure 2: Design overview of the two wheeler

5.5 Switching Mechanism

A key component of this hybrid system is the manual switch that allows the rider to select between the electric motor and the combustion engine. This switch can be a physical toggle or an electronic button, typically located on the handlebar for easy access. When the switch is toggled to the electric mode, the electrical system activates the hub motor, drawing power from the battery. In this mode, the combustion engine is off, resulting in zero emissions and quiet operation.

VI. Calculations

6.1 Design Calculations:

Gross vehicle weight (GVW) = 106+60 KG = 166*9.81 = 1628.46N

Weight on each drive wheel (WW) = 1628.46/2 =814.23N

Radius of wheel/tire (RW) = 0.2159 m

Desired top speed (Vmax) = 50 Kmph =13.889 mps

Maximum incline angle = 12 degrees

Working surface= concrete (good)

Total tractive effort (TTE) requirement for the vehicle: $TTE = RR + GR + AD$

Where:

TTE = Total Tractive Effort [N]

RR = Rolling Resistance [N]

GR = Force required to Climb a Grade [N]

AD = Aerodynamic drag force [N]

VII. Conclusion:

In conclusion, our project represents a significant advancement in sustainable transportation for two-wheelers:

- **Hybrid Power Integration:** By merging electric and internal combustion engines, we maximize efficiency and cater to diverse user needs, enhancing environmental impact mitigation.
- **IoT Empowerment:** Our incorporation of advanced IoT features like GPS tracking and security functionalities ensures unprecedented convenience and safety for riders.
- **Enhanced Security:** We've implemented a robust alarm system to protect against theft, reinforcing trust and safeguarding rider investments.

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